

UNDERSTANDING PREDICTORS OF STATISTICAL COMPETENCY: EXPLORING THE ROLE OF ATTITUDE, EFFORT, ANXIETY AND LEARNING APPROACHES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 4

Pages: 463-475

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1974

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12591659

Manuscript Accepted: 05-27-2024

Understanding Predictors of Statistical Competency: Exploring the Role of Attitude, Effort, Anxiety and Learning Approaches

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Abstract

Statistical competency, characterized by the ability to analyze and interpret data, is crucial in today's research-driven world. This study investigated factors affecting this competency in college students. Using a correlational design, data were collected from 325 students via surveys using stratified random sampling. Results from ordinal logistic regression revealed that factors like effort, degree program (math-related vs. non-math), delivery type (blended vs. modular), and a deep learning approach positively influence competency. Conversely, a surface learning approach has a negative impact. Attitudes, anxiety, and strategic learning approach were not found to be significant predictors. These findings suggest that various factors contribute to statistical competency, and educational strategies should address these diverse influences.

Keywords: *statistic in research, ordinal logistic regression, statistical competency level, deep learning, surface learning*

Introduction

Statistical competency is a skill that has progressed from being a forte to an essential proficiency in the information age. The ability to comprehend, interpret, and apply statistical methods has become a vital tool for individuals across diverse professions and industries to extract meaningful insights from large data sets available. This skill allows individuals to navigate the broad landscape of information, decipher patterns, and understand trends that might otherwise remain hidden. Since the role of statistical competency is important in addressing real-life challenges, tertiary education has incorporated programs that could enhance students' statistical competency. Tertiary education acts like an access for research work in different fields and an effective way of improving skills and knowledge for doing researches (Oguan et al., 2014). The curriculum includes research courses that require students to complete a study related to their fields of expertise. Whether it is a mathematics related program or not, students need to comply with a research paper requirement to be able to graduate. In compliance with the CHED Memorandum Order number 17 series of 2017, a Bachelor of Arts in English Language student requires Language Research II: Thesis. It is also indicated in CHED Memorandum Order number 42 series of 2017 that before conferring a BS Statistics degree, a student should pass the Thesis/Special Problem course. Research, as defined by Babbie (2021), is a systematic inquiry to describe, explain, predict, and control the observed phenomenon. It is a rigorous task but would be a good way to allow students to apply the learnings they have in their program. It will help them develop their critical thinking, organize a logical analysis, and improve their writing skills. They will also have the opportunity to present and defend their arguments.

In preparation for this course, the curriculum includes a Statistics subject to equip them with knowledge and understanding on the proper conduct of research. Statistics, as defined by Walpole (2017), is the branch of science that deals with the collection, organization, presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. The role of statistics in any research activities is very important and crucial as it will direct the proper way of collecting data, employing appropriate tools to analyze and confirm hypothesis based on the results generated. When the sampling procedure is incorrect, estimates would not be reflective of the results obtained from the population. If inappropriate statistical tools are employed, results may be biased and unreliable. In non-statistical disciplines, statistics and research methodologies are required as basic courses (Hassan et al., 2020). Thus, statistical competence is a prerequisite to be able to produce reliable and sensible results.

With the demand of completing a research project, students struggle and develop an apprehension in the conduct of research (Oguan et al., 2014). As Cumming (2013) believes that there is a need to make significant changes in conducting research that focuses also in estimation based on effect sizes, confidence intervals, and meta-analysis, this adds to the challenges of students in completing a research paper. Male & Lumbantoruan (2021) has noted that learning statistics might be difficult to understand because of the lack of knowledge of and low interest in the subject.

According to the study of Oguan (2014), students' negative attitude towards research is associated with the difficulty of learning to conduct research, the number of workloads given to the students, and their anxiety towards the subject. The attitude of students and their statistical anxiety are important in addressing statistical difficulties and serve better in promoting learning and understanding of statistical literacy (Rosli et al., 2017). The study of Mahmud and Osman (2010) also revealed that the attitude shifted positively with the thorough elucidation of the concepts given by the teacher assigned.

At Central Philippines State University, it has been observed that students are having a hard time determining correct sample sizes and choosing appropriate statistical tools to be used in the analysis of their data. While prior research has determined various factors influencing statistical competency, a clearer understanding of how these factors work together is needed to develop effective

educational strategies. Addressing these factors, educators can tailor teaching methods and interventions to support students in improving their level of competency. This prompts the researcher to conduct a study on the level of statistical competency of students towards statistics in research. The researcher wanted to investigate the relationship of attitude, extent of effort, level of anxiety, and learning approaches in producing quality research.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of statistical competency of students towards statistics in research. Specifically, it sought to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1. degree program and
 - 1.2. type of teaching delivery?
2. What is the extent of effort of students towards statistics in research?
3. What is the level of attitude of students towards statistics in research?
4. What is the level of anxiety of students towards statistics in research?
5. What are the students' learning approaches towards statistics in research?
6. What is the level of statistical competency of students towards statistics in research?
7. Do the level of attitude, level of anxiety, extent of effort, students' learning approach, degree program, and type of teaching delivery predict the level of statistical competency of students towards statistics in research?
8. What parsimonious model can best explain the level of statistical competency of students towards statistics in research?

Literature Review

Statistical Competency: Concept and Theoretical Framing

Statistical competence is defined as a feature of character, which characterizes a person's willingness and ability to organize, process, and interpret information needed to implement management processes (Sychenko et al., 2020). For Rumsey (2002), it is defined as the basic understanding which constitutes statistical reasoning as well as statistical thinking. It includes five sub-components: awareness of the data, the basic understanding of statistical concepts and terminology, data production and results, basic interpretation and communication skills. It consists of understanding required modern democracies (Gould, 2017). It is an intricate construct that needs higher order perceptive skills of critical thinking and inference (Sharma, 2017). According to Hassan, Ghaffar, and Zaman (2020), students had low statistical literacy at the undergraduate level. Comprehension on the concepts like sampling techniques, t-test, chi-square and ANOVA was found low but higher performance in other aspects of inferential statistics was recorded (Yolcu, 2012). It was found by Setiawan and Sukoco (2021) that there is a high level of statistical literacy in the use of descriptive statistics. These students can visualize data and have a good grasp of differentiating results of two separate datasets.

The low ability of statistical descriptives and data visualization indicate statistical education problem (Setiawan & Sukoco, 2021) where students tend to develop statistical anxiety (Dykeman, 2011) that eventually affects their academic performance. Learning statistics in schools must be synchronized (Ridgway et al., 2011) and use of various technological advancements (Suhermi & Widjajanti, 2020) can be a way of improving statistical literacy. In the world of big data, statistical literacy is much needed (Engel, 2017). A statistically literate individual can read graphs and understand concepts of variability and center (Buscher, 2022). Statistically literate students can have opportunities to engage in making sense of issues in the society and make data-driven suggestions and decisions (Weiland, 2019).

According to the investigative study on statistical literacy of Hassan, Ghaffar, and Zaman (2020) with 360 participants from six universities in Pakistan, it was found that 46% of the university students have the ability to determine statistical terminologies but has below average understanding of descriptive statistics. This study was able to identify that there is a low statistical literacy in terms of inferential statistics.

The results from the study of Gonulal (2018) discovered that the number of statistics courses taken, quantitative research orientation, and self-training in statistics were the significant predictors of statistical literacy in second language acquisition. From the findings of Yotongyos, Traiwichitkhun, and Kaemkate (2015), it was revealed that undergraduate students had a moderate level of overall statistical literacy in both knowledge and dispositional components. This result was generated from a random sample of 103 undergraduate students of Chulalongkorn University.

Attitudes and Effort towards Learning Statistics in Research

Positive attitudes towards statistics is important. Yolcu (2012) also found out that students have a positive attitude towards statistics. The study attained the results from investigating 1074 eight grade students and employed a correlational analysis to explore on the association of statistical literacy and attitude towards statistics. A research conducted by Koparan and Güven (2014) discovered that project-based learning enabled the students to increase their attitudes towards statistics. Another study conducted by Huynh, Baglin, and Bedford (2014) determined an improvement in the attitude of the students towards statistics after performing island based activity. The study focused on students' enjoyment and interest in statistics and how they value statistics thru exploration and investigation

performed in the island. Further, Rosli and Maat (2017) showed from their research findings that there is a medium and positive association between attitude towards statistics and their performance.

In addition, the research findings of Gopal et. al (2018) that employed multiple linear regression, it was noted that self-efficacy and attitude towards statistics have an influence on the students' statistical engagement. From a random sample of 293 students in a Malaysian university, data generated that the specified variables were found to significantly predict engagement of students in statistics and explained half of its variation.

It was discovered from the research of Garcia-Santillan et al. (2013) that attitude towards statistics is categorized into favorable and unfavorable attitude. It made use of the data gathered from a random sample of 328 university students. A factor analysis was used to generate the results that favorable attitude includes confidence, likeness, and usefulness, while unfavorable attitudes are anxiety and motivation. Further, it was emphasized in the findings that confidence is the factor that most explained the attitude towards statistics.

Delivery Method and Learning Approaches towards Learning Statistics

Assessment of student's performance is an important part of the educational process. The study habits of the students depend on the difficulty of the assessment tools provided to them (Dunham, Yapa & Yu, 2015). According to the findings of Yang (2017), case studies, video demonstration, discussion forums, and mini projects were considered most effective instructional strategies. Case studies are effective because students can use existing studies as a reference to connect and build their own knowledge on the different aspects of research. Due to the need of live demonstrations, videos are helpful and necessary to further learn the concepts. Authors suggested that instructors need to create own videos despite many existing videos online to focus on what the students need. The use of learning management system in teaching may not be the best context for students who are not visual learners (Kauffman, 2015).

It has been found also that courses should be structured around reading materials, lectures, and assignments organized into chapters with clear learning goals in mind. Courses should provide opportunities for peer collaboration and sharing of ideas in order to develop an online community of learners, rather than feelings of isolation (Kauffman, 2015). The quantity of assignment and students' level of learning approach depends on whether the task and materials can lead to students' higher level of learning and the prompt assistance from instructors (Ma, 2015).

Online students used the textbook as their primary source of information to learn new topics, then moved on to homework assignments and online video tutorials. This stresses the importance of having a textbook for online students in addition to some form of lecture replacement such as online video tutorials (Shotwell & Apigian, 2015). Also, instructional design moderates the association between social presence and academic performance, indicating that a course design increases the level of meaningful interactions between students had a significant impact on the development of social presence and thus, could positively affect students' academic performance (Joksimovic, 2015).

A standardized research instrument was devised by Tait and Entwistle (1997). The students' learning study style and approached were categorized into deep, strategic, and surface apathetic approach. Deep approach includes seeking meaning, relating ideas, use of evidence and interest in ideas. Strategic approach means that students are organized in studying, knows how manage their time, monitors effectively and motivates to achieve something. The students whose approaches is surface apathetic has lack of understanding and purpose, has fear to fail and always bounded by syllabus.

Anxiety and Competency

Statistics in research is deemed to be a difficult course for college students. Findings from the study of Peiro-Signes et al. (2021) showed that the level of confidence of a student is necessary and a sufficient condition to attaining a high or low level of anxiety towards statistics. It was further discussed that the role of learning approaches and other attitudes can only be manifested in other causal combinations. The study of Ghani and Maat (2018) tested different components of statistical anxiety which includes statistical fears: anxiety on the exam and the statistical class, fear of asking for help and interpretation concerns. Results found out that there is no significant association between statistical concerns and statistical achievement.

Another study by Levpuscek and Cukon (2022) reported that the highest levels of statistical anxiety were reported by students who perceived mathematics as a threat. Students who were having less enjoyment in mathematics in high school perceived statistics to be a less worthy subject and had a lower computation self-concept. Another research by Macher et al. (2015) concluded that the influence of statistics anxiety may differ over the course of learning, with prior positive influences and negative influences of state anxiety in the examination. Using structural equation modelling, the results directed to a suppression effect between statistics anxiety and performance. The correlation between statistics anxiety and performance is almost nil where state anxiety experienced immediately before and during the examination, statistics anxiety had a small but significant negative influence on performance. Statistics anxiety also had a small but significant positive influence on performance. It has been concluded that statistics anxiety may differ throughout the time of learning the course. It has been suggested by these authors to investigate the influence of statistical anxiety within a longitudinal design to create a possible effective teaching interventions.

Furthermore, statistics anxiety is a useful construct that expresses more general disposition to anxiety (Papousek, 2012). Also, using an artificial neural network for the backpropagation algorithm, Hernández de la Hera et al (2023) discovered a negative impact on of

anxiety towards statistical attitude. It has been concluded from the research that emotional education is necessary in the well-being and teaching the course. Valle et al. (2021) found that using thematic analysis learners who adopted a more performance-avoidance goal orientation approach displayed a higher level of anxiety regardless of the dashboard used. Participants of this study were assigned of three dashboards namely, predictive dashboard, descriptive dashboard and a control dashboard to determine the influence of descriptive and predictive learning analytics dashboard to students' statistical anxiety and motivation in an online course.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a correlational research design. It sought to determine significant relationship between the identified variables. This is an appropriate research design as it determined factors that affect the statistical competency of college students. This provided a statistical model that predicts the competency level of students in learning research and use of statistical tools.

Participants

The participants of the study were third year and fourth year college students at CPSU Main Campus for the second semester of academic year 2022-2023 and at least 18 years old. These students started to work on their research papers or in the process of completing their research.

There were 2104 enrolled students. Using the Cochran formula for sampling determination at 95% level of confidence with 5% margin of error, 325 is the minimum sample size required in the conduct of this research.

Instruments

The research instrument consisted of six parts. Part 1 determined the personal information of the participants that included their degree program and the teaching delivery when they took the Statistics subject. For the statistical competency variable, a researcher-made 40-item questionnaire focusing on identifying scales of measurement of data, sample size determination and sampling techniques, data visualization and presentation, formulating hypothesis, and identifying appropriate statistical tools was used. Scores were categorized into failed, conditional, low, average, thorough and excellent.

To determine the attitude, extent of effort, and level of anxiety of students towards statistics in research, a researcher-made instrument were employed. Each questionnaire is consist of 20 statements where participants can rate from a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is defined to be not describing the participant and 5 to be describing the participant all of the time. Attitude was then categorized into very negative, negative, moderately positive, positive and very positive while effort is categorized into no effort, little effort, moderate effort, good effort and maximum effort. Further, level of anxiety is interpreted as not anxious, mild, moderate, high and very high effort.

To determine the students' learning approaches to learning, the "Approaches and Study Skills Inventory for Students" by Tait, Entwistle, and McCune (1997) was adopted. The questionnaire included 52 questions categorized into three approaches, namely: deep, strategic, and surface.

Procedure

Permission from the University President to conduct a study with the endorsement from the Dean's Office was secured first. A stratified random sampling technique was used in identifying the participants. The researcher sought the help of the subject teachers during the administration of the instrument. The participants took at least 20 minutes to finish answering the instrument which was administered face-to-face.

An informed consent form was signed by the participants signifying that they voluntarily accepted to be part of the study. It was discussed with them that whatever score they got from the quiz-type questionnaire would not affect their grade, and in situations where they would find uncomfortable to participate, this would not affect their performance in the course. All data gathered were consolidated and data cleansing was performed.

Descriptive statistics were used in the first six problems while ordinal logistic regression (OLR) was used in the last problem. OLR is used to model relationship between the ordinal response variable which is the level of statistical competency and explanatory variables which are degree program, type of teaching delivery, attitude, extent of effort, level of anxiety and learning approaches.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed appropriate data collection technique and authorization requests from authorities. An informed consent form was secured first from the participants signifying that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. It was emphasized in the consent form that refusing to participate would not affect their class standing or they might skip specific questions that they were not comfortable or feel embarrassed to answer.

During the collection of data, the researcher avoided the use of offensive or racist terms or language. The profile and responses were confidential. Personal information such as names and contact numbers were not included from the database during the data processing

phase. Moreover, only the researcher was given access to the information shared to make sure its confidentiality. Data were stored in a drive and will be deleted a year after the completion of the study. The researcher made sure that no information was leaked nor was used for other purposes. Section 19 of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 known as the general principles in collection, processing, and retention was strictly followed. Other sections stipulated in this law was placed in highest consideration.

There is no direct monetary benefit or compensation that the participants received and participation did not give adverse effect upon their academic standing. Also, the researcher declared no conflict of interest.

Finally, proper citation and acknowledgment of the research papers/works of previous authors were greatly considered. An email to request permission to adopt instrument was sent to the author prior to its conduct.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Participants

The degree program and the delivery method which the students took a statistics related course are presented in Table 2 through a frequency and percentage distribution table.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Participants (n= 325)*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Degree Program		
Math Related	122	37.54
Non-math Related	203	62.46
Type of Teaching Delivery		
Modular	63	19.38
Blended	262	80.62
Total	325	100.00

Table 1 shows that of the 325 participants, 37.54% or 122 were taking a mathematics-related degree program, while almost 2/3 of the participants were students from any of the specified non-mathematics related degree program.

The data also illustrates that 8 out of 10 participants took any Statistics course through a blended modality. This means that these participants had both modular and virtual classes to discuss and explain statistical concepts needed for research.

Extent of Effort of Students

The second research objective determined the students' extent of effort towards statistics in research. The mean scores were computed along with its standard deviation and descriptive interpretation. These values are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2. *Degree of Effort of Students towards Statistics in Research according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Degree Program			
Math-related	3.45	0.07	Moderate
Non-math related	3.45	0.06	Moderate
Type of Teaching Delivery			
Modular	3.45	0.09	Moderate
Blended	3.45	0.05	Moderate
Overall	3.45	0.79	Moderate

Table 2 displays the degree of effort exerted by students towards statistics in research. It can be noted that students regardless of the degree program they were enrolled in or the teaching delivery they had, exerted moderate effort ($M=3.45$, $SD=0.79$) in learning the course. Students sought additional learning materials through published journals and other book references ($M=3.24$, $SD=1.03$) to fully grasp the subject. As these students are computer softwares proficient, they make good effort ($M=3.88$, $SD=1.07$) in using the internet to understand statistical concepts. Also, students take good effort in reading the modules and learning materials ($M=3.50$, $SD=1.10$) to comprehend the subject. Students also take good effort in keeping their assessment results ($M=3.67$, $SD=1.05$) as future reference.

The results of the degree of effort of students towards statistics in research may imply that there is really a desire to learn the subject. This level seems not too high as students may have the notion that whatever they do to comprehend the lessons, it would take an extra effort to understand it. This can be explained from the results of Widakdo (2017) that project-based learning can be used in teaching statistics to increase ability on the topics.

In terms of strategies to learn the course, students are moderately active ($M=3.43$, $SD=1.07$). Aside from the class session, students are finding other strategies to learn the course. This includes downloading additional materials from the internet and work on practice exercises to be more familiarized on the process. Students are also reading other references and published journals to widen their knowledge of completing research. This means that students feel that statistics is useful in the conduct of their research, are interested

in the subject, and exert effort to learn the processes of statistics in research. The results emphasize that although students want to learn statistics because they found it useful in their life and career in the future; however, their literacy might not be enough to learn the subject. They are interested and willing to exert effort, but they are hesitant as they find the subject difficult. This can happen probably because of the nature of statistics, where many complex formula and theoretical concepts need to be studied and learned.

Level of Attitude of Students

The third research objective determined the students' level of attitude towards statistics in research. The mean scores were computed along with its standard deviation and descriptive interpretation. These values are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3. *Level of Attitude of Students towards Statistics in Research according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Degree Program			
Math-related	3.36	0.07	Moderately Positive
Non-math related	3.27	0.05	Moderately Positive
Type of Teaching Delivery			
Modular	3.23	0.09	Moderately Positive
Blended	3.32	0.05	Moderately Positive
Overall	3.31	0.78	Moderately Positive

Table 3 notes that students have a moderately positive attitude ($M=3.31$, $SD=0.78$) towards research and use of statistical tools. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Yolcu (2012) that students have a positive attitude towards statistics, though it was not detailed as to what extent their positive attitude is. As Gopal et al. (2018) found out also that students has a positive attitude towards statistics and that it would help them to be highly engaged in their learning to perform better in a statistics course.

Further, it was revealed that students have a moderately positive attitude in terms of their confidence in learning statistics in research. According to the findings of Garcia-Santillan (2013), confidence is a factor that most explained the attitude towards statistics. It has also been found that students have a positive attitude towards statistics as an integral part in completing research and believing that they can perform better in completing a research if they have enough knowledge of statistics.

Students experienced either pure modular or blended learning modality in delivering this course revealed that both have a moderately positive attitude towards statistics. This is in agreement with the results conducted by Huynh, Baglin, and Bedford (2014) in that there is an improvement in the attitude of the students towards statistics after performing outdoor activities. These activities made the students more enthusiastic in learning the subject through exploration and investigation. Whatever the learning modality is, students tend to work with a positive attitude towards learning the course. Rosli and Maat (2017) showed from their research findings that there is a medium and positive association between attitude towards statistics and their performance.

Level of Anxiety of Students

The fourth research objective determined the students' level of anxiety towards statistics in research. The mean scores were computed along with its standard deviation and descriptive interpretation. These values are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. *Level of Anxiety of Students towards Statistics in Research according to Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Degree Program			
Math-related	3.37	0.06	Moderate
Non-math related	3.69	0.05	High
Type of Teaching Delivery			
Modular	3.57	0.09	High
Blended	3.57	0.05	High
Overall	3.57	0.76	High

Table 4 shows that overall, students have a severe anxiety ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.76$) towards research and use of statistical tools. This agrees with the results of Ghani and Maat (2018) in that students have anxiety towards learning statistics. This may imply that students are anxious that if they do not know how to perform statistical analysis, it may hinder them in completing their research paper and thus could affect their academic performance.

Looking further into the results, it can be noted that the level of anxiety of students taking mathematics related program is lesser as compared to those non-math students. A mean of 3.37 for math-related program signifies that there is a moderate level of anxiety as compared to the 3.67 mean level of anxiety for those non-math related program. According to Levpuscek and Cukon (2022), students who less enjoy math in high school tend to develop statistical anxiety. This may imply that since their courses do not involve much of mathematical or statistical equations, they will be having a hard time understanding the complexity of statistics.

The results also show that students were severely anxious ($M=4.03, SD=1.04$) that their panel members would not approve their research paper. They are also severely anxious and felt stressed ($M=3.87, SD=1.00$) to think that they have a research paper to work on given that they worry a lot ($M=3.81, SD=1.05$) on giving answers to the Statistics questions given to them. However, students are less anxious ($M=2.95, SD=1.33$) in attending class. This means that they have still the interest and willingness to learn the subject. Findings from the study of Peiro-Signes et al. (2021) showed that the level of confidence of a student is necessary and a sufficient condition to attaining a high or low level of anxiety towards statistics.

It can be noted that whether the students took the subject through modular or blended approach, their level of anxiety is moderate. Both groups attained a mean value of 3.57, which indicates a moderate level of anxiety. There is no difference in the feeling of being anxious to learn the subject in whatever teaching modality they had. As Macher et al. (2015) concluded, the influence of statistics anxiety may differ over the course of learning, which might be the reason why the anxiety level seems to be the same for whatever teaching modality they are into.

Students' Learning Approaches of Students

The fifth research objective determined the students' learning approaches towards statistics in research. The categories where students belong are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Students' Learning Approaches towards Statistics in Research

<i>Profile</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Math-related		
Deep Approach	55	45.08
Strategic Approach	51	41.80
Surface Approach	16	13.11
Total	122	100.00
Non-math related		
Deep Approach	75	36.95
Strategic Approach	80	39.41
Surface Approach	48	23.65
Total	203	100.00
Blended		
Deep Approach	105	40.08
Strategic Approach	107	40.84
Surface Approach	50	19.08
Total	262	100.00
Modular		
Deep Approach	25	39.68
Strategic Approach	24	38.10
Surface Approach	14	22.22
Total	63	100.00

Table 5 illustrates that students taking math-related have a deep approach towards statistics in research. Deep approach involves seeking meaning on the topics being discussed. More than five of the 10 students wanted to relate the ideas into more tangible things and make use of evidence to comprehend the concepts. Students are interested in ideas to further explain the concepts. This is in agreement with the findings of Yang (2017) where he discussed that case studies are effective because students can use existing studies as a reference to connect and build their own knowledge on the different aspects of research. With this approach, students can relate the ideas and can build new knowledge about it. It is also displayed from the table that students taking non-math related courses have a strategic approach in learning statistics in research. Strategic approach includes managing time and organized studying. Students who have this approach are alert to prepare for assessment and can monitor their study time.

They intend to achieve highest possible grades (Brown et. al, 2015). This may imply that students might have problems in managing their time with their other activities and they might not be that organized in studying. It can be implied that the habits of students in studying may not be as organized and strong that leads them to have trouble understanding the course. From the findings of Shotwell & Apigian (2015), students learn from the use of textbook. It is a primary source of information to learn new topics along with assignments and online video tutorials. The quantity of assignment and students' level of learning approach depend on whether the task and materials can lead to students' higher level of learning (Ma et. al, 2015). The approach that is least represented by the students taking math-related courses is the surface approach. This approach has a fear of failure and syllabus-bound that is focused only in complying minimum requirements. They have a routine in memorizing. Both students under blended and modular deliveries can have either deep or strategic approaches. The results tell that whatever the delivery method is, the learning approaches are the same.

Level of Statistical Competency

The sixth research objective determined the students' level of competency towards statistics in research. The mean score and standard deviations are presented in Table 6 along with its grade equivalent and competency level.

Table 6. *Level of Statistical Competency of Students towards Statistics in Research*

Topics	Total Items	Mean Score	SD	Grade Equivalent	Interpretation
Basic Concepts	6	3.99	1.48	83	Average
Sampling Techniques	6	3.38	1.40	78	Low
Data Visualization	7	5.43	1.33	89	Thorough
Test of Hypothesis	7	2.85	1.71	70	Conditional
Use of Statistical Tools	7	2.13	1.27	65	Failed
Data Interpretation	7	3.77	1.39	77	Low
Overall	40	21.55	5.77	77	Low

Table 6 reflects the level of statistical competency of college students. The results show that the students have low competency on statistics in research (MS=21.55, GE=77). This means that the knowledge of students towards statistics in research is low and needs to be improved. Out of the 40-item quiz given, an average score of 21.55, which is equivalent to 77 has been recorded. The mean score did not even reach half of the total items, which implies that students need to improve their competency level. This results is in accordance with the findings of Hassan, Ghaffar, and Zaman (2020) where undergraduate students had low statistical literacy.

Students have thorough competency on data visualization (MS=5.43,GE=89). This means that these students can generate graphs and tables appropriately and can correctly analyze the presented tables. The competency of students on the basic concepts of statistics (MS=3.99, GE=83), which is deemed necessary in the early stage of data analysis, is at the average level. This reveals that students can determine the scales of measurement of their variables and can correctly identify a discrete or continuous data. Coinciding with the findings of Setiawan and Sukoco (2021), there is a high level of statistical literacy in the use of descriptive statistics; so, these students can visualize data and have a good grasp of differentiating results of two separate datasets. However Yotongyos, Traiwichitkhun, and Kaemkate (2015) revealed that undergraduate students had a moderate level of overall statistical literacy in both knowledge and dispositional components. This means that students' statistical competency differs depending on the group they are with.

Competency in terms of identifying appropriate sampling techniques (MS=3.38, GE=78) and interpreting hypothesis (MS=3.77, GE=77) are found to be low. This means that students have a hard time establishing the sampling methods they will use in their data gathering. The low competency level on interpretation data means that the students find it difficult to give suitable meaning on the results generated. However, it was found the knowledge in conducting test of hypothesis (MS=2.85, GE=70) is marked with a conditional grade. As the grading system dictates that a removal exam is given to test whether the student would pass or not, this means that the competency level of students in establishing hypothesis testing needs to be improved. The level of competency in the use of statistical tools (MS=2.13, GE=65) is low. This means that students need to be equipped more with knowledge on how to establish hypothesis statements and determine appropriate statistical tools to be used in analyzing data. These students need to learn more on deciding the results of the hypothesis testing.

The findings seem to agree with the findings of Yolcu (2012) where it discussed that most students could not correctly distinguish the term "samples" presented in the situation. Findings from Aslemand (2018) discussed that students had a hard time determining the difference between two points to measure deviations from the mean and the z-score while in contradiction, Sharma (2017) mentioned that students have the ability to read and interpret statistics or chart where Setiawan and Sukoco (2021) further agreed. Sabbag et al. (2018) mentioned that the ability of students on statistical reasoning can be confirmed by using other tests.

Table 7. *Level of Statistical Competency of Students towards Statistics in Research in terms of Program*

Topics	Total Items	Mean Score	SD	Grade Equivalent	Interpretation
Math Related					
Basic Concepts	6	4.15	1.52	85	Thorough
Sampling Techniques	6	3.77	1.30	81	Average
Data Visualization	7	5.81	1.12	92	Thorough
Test of Hypothesis	7	3.02	1.91	72	Low
Use of Statistical Tools	7	2.12	1.18	65	Failed
Data Interpretation	7	4.19	1.45	80	Average
Overall	40	23.07	6.14	79	Low
Non-Math Related					
Basic Concepts	6	3.90	1.45	83	Average
Sampling Techniques	6	3.14	1.41	76	Low
Data Visualization	7	5.21	1.39	87	Thorough
Test of Hypothesis	7	2.74	1.58	70	Conditional
Use of Statistical Tools	7	2.13	1.18	65	Failed
Data Interpretation	7	3.52	1.30	75	Low
Overall	40	20.64	5.35	76	Low

Presented in Table 7 is that the overall statistical competency of students is low regardless of what program they belong to. However, delving into the different topics in statistics for research, it can be noted that students taking math-related programs tend to be more

competent than those students under the non-math programs. In basic concepts of statistics (M=85, NM=83), students taking math-related programs have a thorough knowledge on this, while non-math students have an average competency on this area.

Students pursuing math-related programs are more competent in determining sampling techniques and sample size (M=81, NM=76). This may mean that these students can develop their sampling design. They are more knowledgeable on the appropriate sample size needed for research. While these students have low competency level in establishing hypothesis, non-math students failed to construct test of hypothesis. Engel (2017) believed that students must possess sound statistical knowledge that includes familiarity with (at least) elementary statistics and appropriate graphical and numerical tools for data representation, along with a capacity for critical thinking and a disposition to engage with evidence. Thus, it can be inferred that whatever degree program a student takes, it must incorporate substantial statistics courses for one to be ready to work with whatever data that one has.

Table 8. *Level of Statistical Competency of Students towards Statistics in Research in terms of Teaching Delivery*

Topics	Total Items	Mean Score	SD	Grade Equivalent	Interpretation
Modular					
Basic Concepts	6	3.63	1.37	80	Average
Sampling Techniques	6	3.27	1.54	77	Low
Data Visualization	7	5.11	1.43	87	Thorough
Test of Hypothesis	7	2.51	1.33	68	Failed
Use of Statistical Tools	7	2.00	1.22	64	Failed
Data Interpretation	7	3.59	1.45	76	Low
Overall	40	20.11	5.06	75	Low
Blended					
Basic Concepts	6	4.08	1.49	84	Average
Sampling Techniques	6	3.40	1.37	78	Low
Data Visualization	7	5.51	1.29	89	Thorough
Test of Hypothesis	7	2.93	1.78	71	Conditional
Use of Statistical Tools	7	2.16	1.29	65	Failed
Data Interpretation	7	3.81	1.41	77	Low
Overall	40	21.90	5.88	77	Low

Table 8 reveals that the statistical competency of students is low regardless of the teaching modality they have. Since the world experienced pandemic that abruptly shifted instruction into non-traditional platforms, students had to right away adjust to the new modality, which may be the reason why competency level has been affected. It can be noted from the table that only the concept on hypothesis testing where difference from the score can be found. Students who took a blended statistics course has higher competency level than those with pure modular modality. This agrees with the results of Seage and Türegün (2020) where they concluded that a blended learning approach has a significant effect on the achievement of students.

Predictors of Statistical Competency using Ordinal Regression Analysis

The seventh and eighth research objectives determined the predictors of statistical competency towards statistics in research. The results of the regression analysis are presented in Tables 8 and 9.

Response Variable. The response variable is the statistical competency of students represented by the scores they obtained from the instrument. This is categorized as failed, low, average, and thorough. This is an ordinal variable as there is a clear ranking of the results. Failed has a lower score from that of a low level, while thorough has a higher score compared to the average level.

Explanatory Variables. The explanatory variables are a combination of categorical and continuous variables. These categorical variables are teaching delivery that was coded 0 for modular and 1 for blended and program that was coded 0 for non-math and 1 for math related. The continuous variables are the extent of effort, level of attitude, and level of anxiety. Learning approaches were coded into three continuous variables, namely: deep, strategic, and surface. These three learning approaches were used as a separate variable from each other.

Table 9. *Ordinal Logistic Regression Results of the Predictors of Statistical Competency*

	Estimate	Exponentiated Estimate	Std error	Wald	Sig
Effort	0.510	1.67	0.15	11.744	0.001**
Deep Approach	0.964	2.62	0.33	8.734	0.003**
Surface Approach	-1.615	0.20	0.33	24.038	0.000**
Program	0.523	1.69	0.21	6.003	0.014**
Teaching Delivery	0.535	1.71	0.27	4.083	0.043**

**Sig at 0.05

The model presented have a good fit. Assumptions of multicollinearity were satisfied for the explanatory variables based on the variance inflation factors. There is no presence of outliers. The explanatory variables in the final models were kept under the consideration of 5% level of significance. The estimated multiplicative effect on the mean statistical competency of a unit increase in each explanatory

variable is displayed in the “Exponentiated Estimate” column in Table 9.

Table 9 displays the significant predictors of students’ statistical competency. It can be noted that the level of attitude, level of anxiety, and strategic learning approach found to be not a significant predictor of competency towards statistics in research. This implies that whatever the attitude of the students towards statistics in research is, their level of statistical competency does not change. Their anxiety towards the course may not be determinant of how well they will perform in class. The strategic learning approach also is not significantly predicting the competency level of students.

It is found that the extent of effort, the program they belong to, the teaching delivery they took the subject, and their surface and deep learning approaches significantly predict the level of competency towards statistics in research. As the extent of effort of the student increases, the likelihood of having a higher statistical competency can be noted. It can be noted that if the extent of effort is high, the odds that the statistical competency is on a higher rank is 1.67 times higher than that of those who have lesser effort.

It is revealed that the program a student is taking can be a predictor of statistical competency. It is noted that having a math related program can predict higher statistical competency than that of those who are taking non-math related programs as indicated by a positive estimate. Further, it can be noted that if the student is taking a math-related course, the odds that the statistical competency is high is 1.68 times as compared to students taking non-math related programs.

It is found that the delivery of the course contributes in its statistical competency. It is noted that having a blended delivery of the course can obtain higher statistical competency than those who received modular classes. The odds of an increase in statistical competency is 1.71 times for those students from blended learning than those for students who received modular classes.

The results revealed that the deep learning approach can affect the statistical competency of students. Relating ideas and using evidences in learning the course contribute to a higher competency level. The odds on increasing the competency level is 2.62 times for those students who know how to put meaning into ideas and relate it than those who are not. It implies that the more the topic is relatable to current situations, students can therefore learn more and can comprehend the concepts better.

It is also discovered that the surface learning approach affects statistical competency. It can be noted as the parameter estimate is negative, the higher the surface learning approach in them, the lower their competency level is. If the surface learning approach is highly manifested in a student, the odds that the student will get a higher statistical competency is just 20% than the odds of those who show lesser surface approach, thus a reduction of 80%. This implies that the more the students fear to fail and just focus on the minimum requirement, their competency level is low.

Students’ competency level cannot be predicted by just the variables included. There are other reasons that affect the competency level of students. The results from the study of Gonulal (2018) discovered that the number of statistics courses taken, quantitative research orientation, and self-training in statistics were the significant predictors of statistical literacy in second language acquisition. In addition, Repedro and Diego (2021) found out that how students value the subject significantly predicts their statistical literacy. Thus, there are indeed different factors that could affect the level of competency of students in statistics in research. Competency level can be attributed to different factors that have yet to be explored. As the Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes, learning the course is a continuous process. It is important to be updated with the innovations that could possibly help the students discover their full potential in statistics in research.

Conclusions

The study investigated on the factors affecting the statistical competency of students towards statistics in research. The findings showed that extent of effort, the degree program of the students, the teaching delivery of the course, and a deep learning approach positively predict the competence level of the students towards statistics in research. As students exhaust effort in learning the course, it can improve their competency level. Also, students who are taking math-related courses tend to have a better statistical competency as compared to those who are taking non-math related programs. Students who underwent a blended teaching delivery tend to have a higher competency level as compared to those who completed the course with pure modular instruction. Students who can relate ideas or have a deep learning approach have a better competency level than those with a lower deep learning approach. The surface learning approach, however, negatively relates with the statistical competency of the students. As a student aims only to at least comply with minimum requirements and has a tendency to fear failure, the statistical competency level decreases also.

The level of attitude, level of anxiety, and the strategic learning approach did not significantly predict statistical competency. Statistical competency involves logical reasoning and analytical skills which can remain integral even under conditions of anxiety. Students may have developed coping strategies to manage their anxiety and thus not affecting their competency. In addition, attitude toward statistics can be influenced by external factors such as educational experiences and cultural perceptions that could not significantly predict the competency level of students. While time management and organization are good traits of students in learning, this strategic approach cannot directly predict statistical competency of students.

Findings further revealed that the statistical competency of the students towards statistics in research is low. Though on a low level, this may not mean that they do not possess the capability to complete a research paper as this is not a sole indicator of such. There is

just a need to improve it by providing more learning materials and a more rigid training to students.

The findings and conclusion of this study imply some recommendations addressed to concerned stakeholders.

Students should determine and be aware of their level of statistical competency and the factors affecting it. This will help them plan on strategies they will use to help them improve their competency level. It is recommended that students will explore additional learning materials and practice solving variety of statistical problems to reinforce understanding the concepts.

The findings of the study also imply that statistics and research teachers should be aware of the factors affecting the competency level of the students. They should carefully plan on how to deliver the course that could effectively grasp by the students. Teachers should select appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of the students. They should plan and provide an environment where learning the course is easier and fun. As deep learning approach positively affects competency of students in statistics in research, it is encouraged that teachers incorporate engaging activities and present case studies that would challenge critical thinking abilities of students. They may also apply statistical concepts to real-world problems where students can see how its importance. They may provide feedbacks on the works of the students for them to improve their outputs.

Moreover, the findings of the study provide a valuable understanding to school administration to revisit the curriculum and identify any gaps or deficiencies in the curriculum and make adjustments as needed to provide a comprehensive and coherent learning experience for students. It is suggested to develop a learning module that could help the students in learning the course. Also, it is suggested that administration will provide access to high-quality instructional materials and technology resources to enhance learning experiences for students.

For future researchers, the current study recommends further possibilities to conduct related studies. Thus, the following are recommended by the researcher: (1) consider increasing the sample size to possibly increase the power of the model; (2) consider including other explanatory variables that could be a significant predictor of statistical competency; and (3) consider employing other modelling techniques. These considerations may improve the predicting power of the model generated. They may be able to discover other factors and thus, more educational strategies and interventions can be devised to improve students' statistical competency.

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